

Optimization of a novel magnetic refrigerator based on the demagnetizing effect using a particle swarm-like algorithm

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The current state of the art of magnetic refrigerator prototyping relies on changes in magnetic field magnitude for promoting heat transfer processes from cold to hot regions. Although this is the most widespread method, some disadvantages arise, such as requiring massive magnets and complex operation mechanisms to alternate the field intensity. Recently, a new operation approach has been proposed using the demagnetizing effect of polycrystalline and anisotropically shaped magnetocaloric materials, which explores the rotation of the magnetic field rather than changes in its magnitude. In this work, we numerically study the performance of a magnetic refrigerator based on this novel approach using a finite element method, considering the half-plate and half-fluid channel model. After performing 92 simulations with random parameters, the no-load temperature span of the system was optimized using a particle swarm-based algorithm to determine the global best. The initial global best from the simulated results was 5.89 K. A new global best of 7.27 K was obtained after applying the algorithm, which represents an increase of over 20%. For the same volume of magnetocaloric material, the temperature span decreases with the inverse aspect ratio. The maximum temperature span of the remaining inverse aspect ratios was successfully determined. In particular, it was possible to increase the temperature span by 22.91% and 18.28% for the inverse aspect ratios 0.26 and 0.4, respectively. This study highlights the feasibility of a novel kind of magnetic refrigerators based on the demagnetizing field.

Keywords: Magnetocaloric effect; Rotating magnetocaloric effect; Demagnetizing effect-based magnetic refrigerator; Particle Swarm

NOMENCLATURE

AMR	Active Magnetic Regenerator
CHEX/HHEX	Cold/Hot Heat Exchangers
GB	Gradient Boosting
HCP	Hexagonal Close-Packed
MCE	Magnetocaloric Effect
MCM	Magnetocaloric Material
ML	Multiple Linear
MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
MR	Magnetic Refrigerator
PSO	Particle Swarm Optimization
RMCE	Rotating Magnetocaloric Effect

Greek

δ	Plates thickness (mm)
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α	Fitting coefficients (-)
Ψ	Loss function (-)
μ_0	Permeability of free space (Hm^{-1})
μ_f	Dynamic viscosity ($\text{Pa} \cdot \text{s}$)
ω	Plates width (mm)
ρ	Density (kgm^{-3})
Ω	Inertia weight (-)

Roman

ΔT	Temperature span (K)
ΔT_{ad}	Adiabatic temperature change (K)
\dot{Q}_{MCE}	Magnetocaloric effect power source (Wm^{-3})
\dot{Q}_{PD}	Heat conversion term for pressure drop (Wm^{-3})
\mathbb{N}/N	Demagnetizing tensor field/ factor (-)
\mathbf{V}_i	Velocity of the i -th particle (-)
\mathbf{X}_i	Position of the i -th particle (-)
$\arg \min_{\mathbf{h}_r}$	Argument of the minimum (-)

B_{appl}	Magnetic flux density of the applied field (T)
C	Specific heat capacity ($\text{Jkg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$)
c_1	Cognitive acceleration coefficient (-)
c_2	Social acceleration coefficient (-)
d	Distance between plates (mm)
EVS	Explained Variance Score (-)
f	Objective function (K)
G_{best}	Global best (-)
H	Effective magnetic field (Am^{-1})
H_{appl}	Applied magnetic field (Am^{-1})
H_d	Demagnetizing field (Am^{-1})
h_r	Small regression trees (-)
k	Thermal conductivity ($\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$)
L	Length (mm)
M	Magnetization (Am^{-1})
P	Period of the cycle (s)
P_{best}	Personal best (-)
T	Temperature (K)
t	Time (s)
T_C	Curie temperature(K)
u	Fluid velocity (ms^{-1})
z	Logistic mapping (-)

1. INTRODUCTION

Magnetic refrigeration is an emerging and efficient technology, allowing an energy consumption reduction of $\approx 35\%$ with respect to the current vapor-compression technology [1]. Additionally, this technology is more eco and human-friendly since it does not use high global warming potential Hydrofluorocarbon gases or explosive/asphyxiant natural refrigerant gases as the working substance [1–3]. The magnetocaloric effect (MCE) displayed by magnetocaloric materials (MCMs) is the basis for the magnetic refrigerator (MR) operation. Conventionally, a MR requires: a fluid for the thermal exchanges between the different components of the refrigerator; an Active Magnetic regenerator (AMR), which is a porous MCM structure that allows the fluid oscillation and convective heat exchanges; a hot and cold heat exchangers (HHEX and CHEX); and a magnetic field source [3, 4].

Magnetic refrigerators can be classified as static, linear reciprocating and rotary devices, depending on the magnetic field dynamics [4]. In static devices, all the parts are at rest with the exception of the working fluid, and electromagnets are usually selected to generate the magnetic field [4, 5]. This is the least common type of device because permanent magnet field sources, such as Halbach cylinders, are usually preferred over electromagnets due to their lower power consumption and lack of Joule heating. Thus, in linear devices, the magnetic field application and removal processes occur through the motion of the magnetic field source over the static regenerator [6]. In other cases, the AMR (or AMRs) moves linearly in and out of the magnetic field [7–9]. In rotary devices, the magnetic field application and removal can be achieved with different methodologies, depending on the structures of the magnetic field source and regenerator. In this case, the magnetic material can rotate to enter and exit the magnetic field region [4, 10, 11], or the magnetic field source can be rotated to periodically apply and remove the magnetic field from the AMR volume [12].

In the context of MR, Halbach cylindrical systems have demonstrated efficient generation of a homogeneous and high-strength magnetic field [4, 13]. Linear devices benefit from using the conventional Halbach cylinder [13, 14]. On the other hand, rotary devices require more complex magnetic field sources, and nested Halbach cylinder arrays can be used [15–17]. In both cases, a significant amount of magnetic material (usually NdFeB) is required to generate a large enough magnetic field inside the Halbach cylinders, which results in a large and heavy assembly, making the magnetic field source the most expensive component of the MR [5, 13, 18].

In addition to the problems associated with the magnetic field source, other factors related to MR performance also hinder its commercialization. It has been thoroughly reported that the demagnetizing factor, determined by the geometry of the material and its orientation relative to the applied field, negatively impacts the MR performance by significantly reducing the effective magnetic field in the MCM [19–21]. This results in a decrease of the adiabatic temperature change and, consequently, in a decrease of the refrigerator efficiency. Consequently, to maximize the MCE for a certain external magnetic field intensity, one should minimize the demagnetizing effect as much as possible. However, if a material is asymmetrically shaped (e.g. a thin plate), it will have different demagnetizing factors depending on the orientation of the external magnetic field. Thus, the effective magnetic field within the MCM may change through a rotation of the external magnetic field while keeping its intensity constant, resulting in a rotating MCE (RMCE) [22, 23]. This phenomenon was first demonstrated by Barclay *et al.* [24] in 1984 and, for a gadolinium (Gd) sheet rotated in a 0.3 T magnetic field, an adiabatic temperature change (ΔT_{ad}) peak larger than 0.7 K was obtained at ≈ 290 K. More recently, Badosa *et al.* [22] and

TABLE I. Thermal properties of the used materials [32–34]. (*) - temperature and magnetic field dependent.

	k [W · m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	C_P [Jkg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	ρ [kgm ⁻³]
Gd	10.5	(*)	7900
Water	0.6	4200	1000
Plastic	0.23	1500	1300
Copper	401	385	8933

our group [23] studied this effect. Badosa *et al.* [22] also considered Gd plates and a magnetic field of 1.6 T, reaching a ΔT_{ad} of 1 K. Finally, our group [23] experimentally obtained for a Gd plate under a 1 T magnetic field a ΔT_{ad} of 1.27 K. We have also found a non-trivial field strength dependency of the RMCE, where the ΔT_{ad} saturates for fields as low as ≈ 0.4 T ($\Delta T_{ad} = 1.15$ K), suggesting that the magnetic field source strength can be reduced in future applications. Another basis for inducing an RMCE is based on magnetocrystalline anisotropy (MCA) [25–28]. Although this intrinsic type of anisotropy leads to an RMCE even in symmetrically-shaped MCMs, it is restricted to monocrystalline or significantly textured polycrystalline materials. We underline that a combination of these two phenomena is possible by producing anisotropically-shaped materials with MCA.

An MR based on the RMCE is more compact, since the magnetic field source is a single Halbach cylinder, with a simple operation based on its rotation or the rotation of the AMR. In this work, we modeled a MR based on the demagnetizing field-induced RMCE, which is available regardless of MCA. Although this possibility has been briefly studied by some authors [22–24], no systematic study and optimization of this type of device has been performed so far. We have optimized the simulated system by combining regression techniques and particle swarm optimization, which is applied in multiple areas of knowledge [29–31]. By using regression algorithms, we found an approximate behavior for the refrigerator performance. We used the bio-inspired particle swarm methodology to find the best solution. We successfully simulated and optimized, for the first time, the performance of a demagnetizing effect-based refrigerator, demonstrating its ability to achieve significant temperature spans and the potential of a new class of MRs.

2. NUMERICAL MODELING

The proposed model design is similar to that of conventional magnetocaloric refrigerators, also incorporating the AMR, CHEX, HHEX and water as the working fluid. For our model, we considered an ordered structure with parallel plates of Gd as AMR. The CHEX/HHEX are made of copper. We also added plastic flow guides between the Gd plates and the CHEX/HHEX to ensure laminar flow. The properties of the materials used in

the simulations can be found in Table I. In contrast to conventional MR systems, the operation of the proposed refrigerator depends on the demagnetizing effect. The effective magnetic field, \mathbf{H} , inside a given magnetic material is described by the sum of the applied (\mathbf{H}_{appl}) and demagnetizing (\mathbf{H}_{d}) fields:

$$\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{H}_{\text{appl}} + \mathbf{H}_{\text{d}}. \quad (1)$$

The demagnetizing field of the magnetic material can be written as

$$\mathbf{H}_{\text{d}} = -\mathbb{N} \cdot \mathbf{M}, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbb{N} is the demagnetizing tensor that depends only on the geometry, and \mathbf{M} is its magnetization [20, 35]. For a rectangular prism with length L , width ω , and thickness δ ($L \geq \omega > \delta$), the demagnetizing tensor is represented by a symmetric matrix and satisfies [36]:

$$\text{Tr}(\mathbb{N}) = N_L + N_\omega + N_\delta = 1, \quad (3)$$

where N_L , N_ω and N_δ are the demagnetizing factors. Thus, in our model, the magnetic flux density of the applied magnetic field remains constant over time ($B_{\text{appl}} = \mu_0 \cdot H_{\text{appl}} = 1$ T), and only the direction of the applied magnetic field varies. For that, a Halbach cylinder can be used and its rotation allows the application of magnetic field on the parallel plate AMR with different relative orientations. Let us consider a Gd plate with length L_{Gd} , width ω , and thickness δ . The demagnetizing effect is predominant when \mathbf{H}_{appl} is applied along the thickness of the plates ($\mathbf{H}_{\text{appl}} \parallel \delta$), i.e., the internal magnetic field intensity is lower than the one obtained when the \mathbf{H}_{appl} is parallel to the length ($\mathbf{H}_{\text{appl}} \parallel L_{Gd}$). However, since we consider the axial rotation of the Halbach and the length of the plates is along the Halbach axis, the incidence of the magnetic field direction will vary between parallel to the width ($\mathbf{H}_{\text{appl}} \parallel \omega, \perp \delta$) and parallel to the thickness ($\mathbf{H}_{\text{appl}} \parallel \delta, \perp \omega$), which will generate a significant difference between the internal magnetic field intensities of the plates.

Figure 1(a) shows the four stages of the proposed refrigeration process based on Brayton cycles. Given the direction of \mathbf{H}_{appl} generated by the Halbach cylinder, the internal magnetic field will be larger during stages (2) and (3), $H_2, H_3 > H_1, H_4$. The cycle starts when $\mathbf{H}_{\text{appl}} \parallel \delta$ (1), the position that minimizes the internal magnetic field. Then, the Halbach cylinder and, consequently, \mathbf{H}_{appl} rotate by 90° ($1 \rightarrow 2$; $\mathbf{H}_{\text{appl}} \parallel \delta \rightarrow \mathbf{H}_{\text{appl}} \parallel \omega$), resulting in an increase in the AMR temperature due to the internal magnetic field increase. Then, the fluid flows from CHEX to HHEX ($2 \rightarrow 3$), which will release heat to the surroundings, allowing the decrease of the AMR temperature. The Halbach cylinder rotates back to its initial position, reducing the internal magnetic field and the AMR temperature ($3 \rightarrow 4$; $\mathbf{H}_{\text{appl}} \parallel \omega \rightarrow \mathbf{H}_{\text{appl}} \parallel \delta$).

FIG. 1. (a) Brayton-based refrigeration cycle. In $1 \rightarrow 2/3 \rightarrow 4$, the external magnetic field generated by the Halbach cylinder rotates, increasing/decreasing the plate's internal magnetic field. In $2 \rightarrow 3/4 \rightarrow 1$, the fluid flows to the HHEX/CHEX. (b) Side view of the main elements, with the highlight of the half-unit structure considered for the 2D modeling. The blue, gray, green, and red sections represent the CHEX, the plastic flow guides, the MCM and the HHEX, respectively.

Finally, the fluid flows from HHEX to CHEX ($4 \rightarrow 1$), increasing the system temperature slightly. This process repeats periodically to achieve a gradual temperature reduction in the CHEX over time.

Several parameters, such as water flow velocity (v), cycle period (P), spacing between plates (d), CHEX/HHEX length (L_{CHEX}/L_{HHEX}), and plates inverse aspect ratio (δ/ω), were varied as described in Table II to conduct a comprehensive study of the refrigerator performance. Since increasing the amount of MCM used will inevitably lead to more cooling power, the aspect ratio of the plates was varied so that their total length and volume are kept constant at 20 mm and 200mm^3 , respectively, corresponding to a mass of 1.58 g of gadolinium per plate. The length of the flow guides placed between the Gd plates and CHEX/HHEX also remained constant

throughout the simulations, $L_{plastic} = 3.5$ mm.

To efficiently perform the simulations, we considered a half-plate and half-fluid channel model as depicted in Fig. 1(b). This approach is widely used in the literature [34, 37–39] due to its effective use of symmetry, incorporating two symmetry planes: one crosses the fluid channel and another the regenerator components. This method significantly reduces the complexity and computational cost of the simulated model. Similarly to the work previously developed by the authors in Ref. [40], the exterior boundaries are thermally insulated, i.e. $-\hat{\mathbf{n}} \cdot \mathbf{q} = 0$, where $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ is the normal vector to the boundary and \mathbf{q} is the heat flux. Also, a triangular mesh with elements of variable size was used. The selected elements have a minimum and maximum size, ensuring that, when the mesh is generated, elements of different sizes fit perfectly into the

Parameter	Values
P [s]	[2, 24]
v [mm/s]	[0.09, 1.7]
d [mm]	[0.2, 1.875]
δ/ω	$\begin{cases} 0.1 & \delta = 1, \omega = 10 \\ 0.16 & \delta = 1.25, \omega = 8 \\ 0.26 & \delta = 1.6, \omega = 6.25 \\ 0.4 & \delta = 2, \omega = 5 \\ 0.63 & \delta = 2.5, \omega = 4 \\ 0.98 & \delta = 3.125, \omega = 3.2 \end{cases}$
$L_{CHEX/HHEX}$ [mm]	[5, 20]

TABLE II. For the study, the cycle period (P), fluid velocity (v), spacing between plates (d), inverse aspect ratio (δ/ω), and length of the CHEX/HHEX were varied (.

system geometry [41]. The selection of the number of grid elements and the time step was made considering the results previously obtained and detailed in Ref. [40].

Governing equations

The numerical simulation of this system requires the application of the characteristic heat transfer equations, which include the heat transfer flux occurring in the system and heat conversion processes. The heat transfer includes the thermal conduction between solid-state components and the heat transfer phenomena between each of these components and the fluid. Heat conversion processes involve the conversion of energy from, or to, heat, e.g. fluid friction or MCE. The thermodynamic description was made by taking into account Ref. [3] and considering the heat conversion term of the MCE (\dot{Q}_{MCE} , obtained with Eq. 15), the heat transfer terms between the MCM and fluid (\dot{Q}_s^f), MCM and the cold side flow guide (\dot{Q}_s^{Cfg}), and between MCM and the hot side flow guide (\dot{Q}_s^{Hfg}) [3]:

$$\rho_s C_s \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{k}_s \nabla \mathbf{T}_s) + \dot{Q}_{MCE} + \dot{Q}_s^f + \dot{Q}_s^{Cfg} + \dot{Q}_s^{Hfg}, \quad (4)$$

where the subscript s stands for the solid MCM, Cfg stands for the flow guide between MCM e CHEX, and Hfg stands for the flow guide between MCM e HHEX. Here ρ is the density, C the specific heat at constant field, T the temperature, k the thermal conductivity. For the heat transfer fluid,

$$\rho_f C_f \left(\frac{\partial T_f}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) T_f \right) = \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{k}_f \nabla \mathbf{T}_f) + \dot{Q}_{PD} + \dot{Q}_f^s + \dot{Q}_f^{CHEX} + \dot{Q}_f^{HHEX} + \dot{Q}_f^{Cfg} + \dot{Q}_f^{Hfg}, \quad (5)$$

where the fluid is denoted by the subscript f , \dot{Q}_{PD} is the heat conversion term that includes the pressure drop, \dot{Q}_f^s , \dot{Q}_f^{CHEX} , \dot{Q}_f^{HHEX} , \dot{Q}_f^{Cfg} and \dot{Q}_f^{Hfg} describe the heat transfer between the fluid and MCM, between fluid and CHEX, between fluid and HHEX, and between the fluid and both flow guides, respectively. Other heat equations for the thermodynamic description of CHEX and HHEX were also considered. For the CHEX, the associated heat equation is given by

$$\rho_{CHEX} C_{CHEX} \frac{\partial T_{CHEX}}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{k}_{CHEX} \nabla \mathbf{T}_{CHEX}) + \dot{Q}_{CHEX}^f + \dot{Q}_{CHEX}^{Cfg}, \quad (6)$$

where \dot{Q}_{CHEX}^f and \dot{Q}_{CHEX}^{Cfg} are heat transfer terms that characterize the heat transfer between the fluid and the CHEX, and between the cold flow guide and the CHEX, respectively. Similarly, for the HHEX, we have

$$\rho_{HHEX} C_{HHEX} \frac{\partial T_{HHEX}}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{k}_{HHEX} \nabla \mathbf{T}_{HHEX}) + \dot{Q}_{HHEX}^f + \dot{Q}_{HHEX}^{Hfg}, \quad (7)$$

where \dot{Q}_{CHEX}^f and \dot{Q}_{HHEX}^{Hfg} are the heat transfer terms describing the heat transfer between the fluid and the HHEX, and between the hot flow guide and the HHEX, respectively. Regarding the cold and hot side flow guides, we have

$$\rho_{Cfg} C_{Cfg} \frac{\partial T_{Cfg}}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{k}_{Cfg} \nabla \mathbf{T}_{Cfg}) + \dot{Q}_{Cfg}^f + \dot{Q}_{Cfg}^{CHEX} + \dot{Q}_{Cfg}^s, \quad (8)$$

and

$$\rho_{Hfg} C_{Hfg} \frac{\partial T_{Hfg}}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{k}_{Hfg} \nabla \mathbf{T}_{Hfg}) + \dot{Q}_{Hfg}^f + \dot{Q}_{Hfg}^{HHEX} + \dot{Q}_{Hfg}^s, \quad (9)$$

respectively. The first term in the previous six equations represents the thermal conduction between solid-state components. Regarding the heat transfer terms, we have the particular cases $\dot{Q}_s^f = -\dot{Q}_f^s$, $\dot{Q}_{CHEX}^f = -\dot{Q}_f^{CHEX}$, $\dot{Q}_{HHEX}^f = -\dot{Q}_f^{HHEX}$, $\dot{Q}_{Cfg}^f = -\dot{Q}_f^{Cfg}$, $\dot{Q}_{Hfg}^f = -\dot{Q}_f^{Hfg}$, $\dot{Q}_{Cfg}^s = -\dot{Q}_f^{Cfg}$ and $\dot{Q}_{Hfg}^s = -\dot{Q}_f^{Hfg}$. Each one of these terms can be defined by

$$\dot{Q}_o^t = h_o^t (T_o - T_t), \quad (10)$$

where the indices o and t denote the origin and the target, respectively. Here h is the heat transfer coefficient between o and t [3, 41].

The fluid velocity vector is denoted by $\mathbf{u} = (u_x, u_y, 0)$. Regarding the fluid dynamics, one must solve the Navier-Stokes equations [40]:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} = \frac{\mu_f}{\rho_f} \nabla^2 \mathbf{u} - \frac{1}{\rho_f} \nabla p \quad (11)$$

and

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0, \quad (12)$$

where μ_f is the dynamic viscosity and p the pressure [19]. To solve this equation, one can define the pressure scalar field p , which can be approximated by fixing pressure p_1 at one end and pressure p_2 at the other [3]. In this model, we directly defined the velocity at the inlet and outlet using the values presented in Table II. The pressure drop was also considered in our model. With generality, the heat conversion term for the pressure drop can be defined specifically by [3]

$$\dot{Q}_{PD} = \left| \mathbf{u} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \right|, \quad (13)$$

where the pressure drop ratio $\frac{\partial p}{\partial x}$ depends on the regenerator geometry. Since we are considering a parallel plate geometry, the pressure drop ratio is evaluated via Darcy-Weisbach equation [42–44]:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = f \frac{\rho_f u^2}{2D_h}. \quad (14)$$

Here D_h is the hydraulic factor and $f = \frac{96}{Re}$ is the friction factor, where $Re = \left(\frac{\rho D_h u}{96\mu} \right)$ is the Reynolds number. However, in some 2D models the pressure drop is defined as a fixed boundary condition [3, 34]. In our case, since we used the software *COMSOL Multiphysics* software, the pressure drop is automatically included in the numerical equations.

Finally, the RMCE was simulated using the ΔT_{ad} power source method, which provides accurate results for RMCE simulations while also saving computational resources compared to the continuous temperature change method. Thus, a heat power pulse was used to vary the MCM temperature by ΔT_{ad} [40]:

$$\dot{Q}_{MCE} = \frac{\rho_S C_S \Delta T_{ad}(T)}{\tau}, \quad (15)$$

where τ is the time interval during which an increase/decrease of the effective magnetic field occurs using a short power pulse. In this approach, the \dot{Q}_{MCE} term differs from zero only when the direction of the applied magnetic field rotates from one side to the other by 90°. This method was implemented in COMSOL using a heat source and considering four discrete steps. The cycle period of the ΔT_{ad} power source method includes the

time interval in which the effective magnetic field is maximized (*stage* == 0), followed by a time interval of duration τ to rotate the magnetic field (*stage* == 1). This is then followed by the time interval during which the effective magnetic field is minimized (*stage* == 2), and finally, a time interval of duration τ to rotate the magnetic field, returning it to the initial position (*stage* == 3). These stages were used as conditions to change the power source state, such that:

$$\begin{cases} \text{if } stage == 0, & \dot{Q}_{MCE} = 0 \\ \text{if } stage == 1, & \dot{Q}_{MCE} = -\frac{\rho_S C_S \Delta T_{ad}(T)}{\tau} \\ \text{if } stage == 2, & \dot{Q}_{MCE} = 0 \\ \text{if } stage == 3, & \dot{Q}_{MCE} = \frac{\rho_S C_S \Delta T_{ad}(T)}{\tau} \end{cases}, \quad (16)$$

For the simulations, we defined $\tau = 0.05$ s in accordance with the time step Δt , which has the same value. Note that we considered an abrupt magnetic field change, using a square wave similar to the one described in Ref. [40]. With this approach, it is expected that the results will not deviate significantly from reality. Although it may impact the results quantitatively for larger periods, the qualitative conclusions will remain the same.

Model Validation

The numerical model was validated, considering the results obtained with the numerical model of Petersen *et al.* [34, 45]. This model uses an AMR with a Gd parallel plate structure, considering the half-unit structure again (Fig. 1(b)). It was considered that $L_{Cd} = 50$, $L_{CHEX} = L_{HHEX} = 20$, $\delta = 1$ and $d = 1$ mm, with a gap of 10 mm between the heat exchangers and regenerator. We also defined a fluid flow velocity of 2 mm/s, a cycle period of 6 s, and a material with low thermal conductivity was placed between the heat exchangers and regenerator to ensure laminar flow. The thermal properties of the materials can be found in Table I. The HHEX temperature was fixed at 298 K, while only the temperature of the HHEX and the Gd plate were measured. Thus, the performance was evaluated for 5000 s, and a no-load temperature span of 10.6 K was obtained (Fig. 2), which has a deviation of only 2.75% from the value obtained by Petersen *et al.* [34] (10.9 K). Note that after 3000 s 97% of the final temperature span is reached, which is a result and time similar to that of Silva *et al.* [45] (reported 98%) and Petersen *et al.* [34] to reach the steady state.

Rotating Magnetocaloric Effect

The demagnetizing factor takes different values considering the orientation of the applied magnetic field, which impacts the internal magnetic field of the MCM. The RMCE is the result of the change in the internal magnetic

FIG. 2. Temperature variations in the CHEX and MCM as a function of time for the validated system.

field induced by the demagnetizing effect [22–24]. In the conventional MCE, the peak of the adiabatic temperature change (ΔT_{ad}) upon H -application/removal occurs near the Curie temperature of the MCM ($T_C = 293$ K for Gd) [34, 40]. In the case of the RMCE, the maximum ΔT_{ad} was obtained for ≈ 286 K (see *Supporting Information*). Furthermore, while the conventional MCE has a maximum ΔT_{ad} of 4.22 K, the RMCE shows a maximum of 1.61 K for $\delta/\omega = 0.1$.

For the present work, the specific heat and adiabatic temperature change of the MCM, Gd, were calculated through simulations of a hexagonal close-packed (HCP) spin 7/2 Ising model, described and experimentally validated in Ref. [23]. We determined the thermodynamic properties through Monte Carlo sampling of its energy- and magnetization-dependent Joint Density of States (JDoS). It was assumed the full energy-magnetization phase space of the spin 7/2, 128 sites, 12 nearest-neighbor HCP lattice, with no energy or magnetization binning. This phase space is quite large, with 897×18817 ($E \times M$) total states considered [23]. In this model, a JDoS was estimated using the Flat Scan Sampling method described in Ref. [46]. Each macrostate (E, M) was sampled 10^6 times. The magnetic exchange parameter J (≈ 5.3 meV) was chosen to obtain the experimentally observed T_C value of Gd. The total specific heat (with phonon and magnetic components), was estimated considering the phonon contribution of a Debye model with $T_D = 169$ K and the magnetic specific heat of the HCP spin 7/2 Ising lattice [47]. The RMCE was simulated by implementing the ΔT_{ad} power source method (Eq. 15), noting that the \dot{Q}_{MCE} term differs from zero only when the magnetic field is rotated from one position to another.

3. OPTIMIZATION

Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) is an optimization technique inspired by social behavior and interaction between individuals belonging to large groups, e.g., bird flocking, fish schooling, and insect swarming [48]. This meta-heuristic algorithm has been used in various areas such as in engineering [29, 49, 50], medicine for disease diagnosis [30, 51], pharmaceuticals [31] and economics [52] due to its easy implementation and fast convergence to the optimal solution. In this work, the performance of the refrigerator was evaluated in terms of the temperature span, defined as:

$$\Delta T = T_{HHEX} - T_{CHEX}, \quad (17)$$

where T_{HHEX} and T_{CHEX} are the temperatures of the HHEX and CHEX, respectively. To simplify the testing of the refrigerator’s operation, we measured the temperature span after the CHEX temperature stabilized, i.e., when no cooling load was applied. This approach allows solving a single-objective optimization problem, without scaling to a multi-objective problem. Thus, initially, a population of N particles is randomly generated, where each particle represents a possible solution. The position \mathbf{X}_i and velocity \mathbf{V}_i of the i -th particle are updated to reach the best solution (in this case the maximum ΔT) of the objective function $f(\mathbf{X})$ [53, 54]. For clarification, the position of each particle is described by the input parameters, i.e. $v, P, d, \delta/\omega$ and $L_{CHEX/HHEX}$. We implemented three different regression algorithms using the library *scikit-learn* of the Python programming language to obtain the objective function. The developed PSO-based algorithm is detailed below.

FIG. 3. Flowchart of the used particle swarm-based algorithm.

Objective function

Given a set of vectors whose inputs are the k parameters to be studied ($\{\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}\}$), the goal of regression algorithms is to create and then train a function to predict a continuous value [55]. First, we considered multiple linear (ML) regression, where a linear equation is used to

fit the trained data [56]:

$$f(\mathbf{X}) = \alpha_0 + \sum_{j=1}^k \alpha_j X_j, \quad (18)$$

where α are the fitting coefficients. Then, the nonlinear multilayer perceptron (MLP) regressor, also known as

a feed-forward neural network, was considered. In this case, the data flows from the input to the output layer through at least one hidden layer [55, 57]. We set 5000 as the maximum number of iterations, 100 neurons in the hidden layer, the rectified linear unit function as the activation function for the hidden layer, and the Adaptive Moment Estimation (AdaM) solver for weight optimization.

Finally, we considered gradient boosting (GB) regression, which intends to combine the output of many "weak learners" in the form of a summation [58, 59]:

$$f(\mathbf{X}) = \sum_{r=0}^R h_r(\mathbf{X}), \quad (19)$$

where R is the number of weak models and h_r are small regression trees of fixed size. In each boosting iteration r , a new regression tree is added to the model, which results in the sum of r small regression trees,

$$f_r(\mathbf{X}) = f_{r-1}(\mathbf{X}) + h_r(\mathbf{X}). \quad (20)$$

Note that h_r is trained by minimizing a given loss function:

$$h_r = \arg \min_{h_r} \sum_{i=1}^N \Psi(Y_i, f_{r-1}(X_i) + h_r(X_i)). \quad (21)$$

In this case, the loss function to be optimized was squared error. We also considered 500 weak learners, which corresponds to the number of boosting stages to perform, and a learning rate of 0.1.

To evaluate the quality of the used regressors, we considered the explained variance score (EVS), which is the ratio between the variance of the absolute error and the variance of the correct value. The EVS is then a measure of the error dispersion in a given data set, being estimated by [60]:

$$EVS(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) = 1 - \frac{Var(\mathbf{Y} - f(\mathbf{X}))}{Var(\mathbf{Y})}, \quad (22)$$

where Var represents the variance. This value ranges between 0 and 1, where 1 is the best result.

Particle Swarm-based Algorithm

After obtaining the objective function, the following steps of the proposed algorithm are performed as illustrated in Fig. 3. The population of $N_{particles}$ is initialized with random positions and velocities. The fitness of each particle in the initial population is evaluated considering the objective function $f(\mathbf{X})$ and the initial position.

Then, the position and velocity of the particles are updated according to [48, 53, 54, 61]:

$$V_{\kappa}^{i+1} = \Omega V_{\kappa}^i + c_1 r_1 \cdot (P_{best, k}^i - X_{\kappa}^i) + c_2 r_2 \cdot (G_{best}^i - X_{\kappa}^i), \quad (23)$$

and

$$X_{\kappa}^{i+1} = X_{\kappa}^i + V_{\kappa}^{i+1}. \quad (24)$$

Here, Ω is the inertia weight, the parameters r_1 and r_2 are randomly generated numbers in the range $[0, 1]$, while c_1 and c_2 are cognitive and social acceleration coefficients, respectively. P_{best} and G_{best} are the personal and global best, respectively. The term $c_1 r_1 \cdot (P_{best, k}^i - X_{\kappa}^i)$ is related to the individual behavior of each particle in order to learn and evolve from its previous results, the term $c_2 r_2 \cdot (G_{best}^i - X_{\kappa}^i)$ shows the evolution of each particle by taking into account the "social influence" [53, 61, 62]. For the simulations, we defined $c_1 = c_2 = 2.5$, so that the individualism of each particle is as relevant as the social factor. The inertia weight Ω is used to control the particle velocity and, from the different existing strategies, we considered the chaotic inertia weight approach due to its reported accuracy when solving different problems. The chaotic inertia weight is formulated as [61, 63]:

$$\Omega^i = (\Omega_1 - \Omega_2) \cdot \frac{MAXiter - i}{MAXiter} + \Omega_2 \cdot z, \quad (25)$$

where $\Omega_1 = 0.4$ and $\Omega_2 = 0.9$ are the original values, $MAXiter$ is the maximum number of iterations of the PSO-based algorithm, i is the current iteration and z corresponds to a logistic mapping given by:

$$z = \mu \cdot z_r \cdot (1 - z_r). \quad (26)$$

The value of z_r is a random number between 0 and 1, while $\mu = 4$ was selected to induce chaotic phenomena [63]. This methodology allows to introduce even more randomness in the movement of the particles and a mechanism that helps to escape from local maxima.

After updating the velocity and position of each particle, its fitness was evaluated, and then the swarm's personal and global best were also updated. This process repeats as schematized in the Fig. 3 if the stopping criteria are not met. Although in the literature only one stopping criterion is usually selected, in this work we considered two. The first occurs when all the particles converge towards the updated G_{best} . We also considered the possibility that all particles may not converge to the same value of G_{best} after a defined large number of iterations ($N_{iterations}$), and its P_{best}^{min} can converge individually. Hence, we added the second stopping criterion, in which, if the number of iterations is very large and the P_{best} of the particle with minimum value converges, the algorithm stops. To evaluate if the choice of parameters,

FIG. 4. (a) Temperature variation of the demagnetizing effect-based MR over time for different input parameters. (b) Histogram of the 92 obtained results.

inertia weight calculation methodology, and stopping criteria was suitable, we conducted a particle convergence study using mathematical benchmark test functions, as detailed in the *Supporting Information*.

4. RESULTS

For the present model, T_{HHEX} is fixed at 293 K and is equal to the initial temperature. By using the *COMSOL Multiphysics* software (version 5.6), we performed 92 simulations of the demagnetizing effect-based MR by varying the input parameters according to the ranges specified in Table II. Figure 4(a) exemplifies the performance of the refrigerator considering different input parameters, leading to distinct no-load temperature spans ($\Delta T = 5.47, 3.17, 1.39, 0.79, 0.68$ and 0.04 K). Thus, by varying the input parameters, a broad interval of temperature span values was achieved, ranging from values approaching 0 to values close to 6 K (Fig. 4(b)). Before performing any analysis of the simulated dataset, the largest temperature span of 5.89 K was obtained for $P = 3$ s, $v = 1.11$ mm/s, $d = 0.2$ mm, $\delta/\omega = 0.1$ and $L_{CHEX}/HHEX = 17$ mm.

The dataset was divided into train and test sets. We used approximately 80% of the data for training, and the remaining 20% was used for testing. Both data-sets were randomly selected. We computed 200 iterations of randomly selected datasets for training and testing to determine which regressor should be used as the objective function. Then, the EVS of each iteration was calculated for each regressor. Figure 5 shows histograms with the results obtained for the three regressors. One can notice that lower EVS values were obtained for the ML regressor (Fig. 5(a)), even reaching values below 0.5, indicating

overall poor performance. For the MLP regressor (Fig. 5(b)), it was possible to observe a performance improvement since there was an increase in counts for EVS larger than 0.9. However, the GB regressor (Fig. 5(c)) presented the best results since most values range between 0.9 and 1. For this reason, the GB regressor was selected to provide the objective function.

After that, 80 data results were randomly selected for training and 12 for testing. In this case, the GB regressor has an EVS of 0.92. Considering 500 particles and a maximum number of 2000 iterations, we then used our algorithm to obtain the best solution. The position and velocity of 500 particles were randomly generated, with an initial global best of 4.85 K. Convergence is achieved after 202 iterations with the best solution of 6.42 K being predicted to occur for $P = 2$ s, $v = 1.68$ mm/s, $d = 0.2$ mm, $\delta/\omega = 0.1$ and $L_{CHEX}/HHEX = 19$ mm. This predicted value represents an increase of 9% in the maximum ΔT ($= 5.89$ K), obtained in the simulated dataset. Figure 6(a) shows the convergence phenomenon of 30 particles over the course of 202 iterations. Note that each particle only changes its position if the current result is better than the previous, which can explain the abrupt ΔT changes. However, the temperature span of the best simulated result was 7.27 K, which has an absolute error of 0.85 K compared to the predicted value (Fig. 6(b)). This result represents an increase of 23.43% compared to the best result of the previously simulated dataset.

From the obtained results, one can observe that the temperature span decreases with δ/ω , which intuitively is expected since the adiabatic temperature peak of the RMCE also decreases with δ/ω (see Fig. 7 in *Supporting Information*). This decrease can be observed in Table III and Fig. 6(b). We then fixed the value of δ/ω to predict the global best of the remaining five inverse as-

FIG. 5. Iterative study of EVS for (a) ML, (b) MLP and (c) GB regressors.

pect ratios ($\delta/\omega = [0.16, 0.26, 0.4, 0.63, 0.98]$). We successfully determined the coordinates of the global best for each δ/ω . For $\delta/\omega = 0.16$ and 0.4 , notable ΔT increments of 22.91% and 18.28% were obtained, respectively, after the application of the algorithm. On the other hand, for $\delta/\omega = 0.26, 0.63,$ and 0.98 , the ΔT associated with the global best coordinates corresponded to values very close to the maximum ΔT in the simulated dataset. Note that for larger values of δ/ω , it was more difficult to predict the maximum ΔT value, particularly for $\delta/\omega = 0.98$. This occurred because the respective ΔT values are very small compared those generated by the remaining inverse aspect ratios. This problem could

be solved by performing more simulations and increasing the dataset size. However, each simulation in COMSOL takes between 2 and 4 days due to the large complexity of the numerical model and this would be an excessively time-consuming process.

Our best simulated result ($\Delta T = 7.27$ K) is within the same order of magnitude of some conventional magnetic refrigerator models [34, 37, 38, 45, 64]. Petersen *et al.* [34] obtained a no-load temperature span of 10.9 K, for a cycle period of 6 s. Considering the same model as Petersen but a different simulation methodology, Silva *et al.* obtained a no-load temperature span of 11.6 K [45]. Considering different parameters and a period of 2 s, You *et al.* obtained a temperature span of 12.5 K [38]. More recently, Yuan *et al.* [65] numerically demonstrated that using multi-layered regenerators with first-order MCMs allows to obtain temperature spans up to 30 K. Regarding experimental prototypes, one can find conventional magnetic prototypes that significantly outperform ours [66–68]; it has been reported that the maximum temperature span under no-load achieved was 42.28 K [68]. On the other hand, our simulated refrigeration system outperforms some simple solid-state magnetic refrigerators in terms of temperature span. Numerical models with temperature spans ranging between 1.12 and 4.59 K can be found in the literature [9, 45, 69, 70]. In these cases, it has been shown that the use of magnetic field application/removal asymmetrical cycles [9] and magnetic field acceleration/deceleration mechanisms [71] can significantly improve performance. As a first approach, our results are promising; yet, in the future, to create competitive magnetic refrigerators based on the demagnetizing effect, one should incorporate asymmetric cycles, different modes of magnetic field application and removal, multi-layered regenerators, and/or different MCMs.

For this type of device, the large amount of magnetic material used in conventional magnetic refrigerators is not necessary, since the Halbach only needs to rotate to generate the RMCE in the MCM. Additionally, lower magnetic fields can be used in the future, decreasing even more the amount of magnetic material in the magnetic field source. This device will consume less energy and will only require periodically rotating the Halbach and moving the pistons. However, this energy consumption will increase as the device is scaled for commercial applications. Maintenance is expected to be similar to that of a conventional magnetic refrigerator, as the components are the same.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A new class of magnetic refrigerators based on the demagnetizing effect was numerically investigated, with a refrigeration process based on the well known Brayton cycle. We performed 92 simulations with *COMSOL Multiphysics*, by varying the period, fluid velocity, spacing between Gd plates, inverse aspect ratio, and the

FIG. 6. (a) Convergence of 30 particles to the global best after 202 iterations. (b) Temperature variation over time for the maximum temperature span of each δ/ω .

Inverse aspect ratio	Best ΔT before PS	$(P, v, d, L_{CHEX/HHEX})$ predicted	G_{best} predicted	G_{best} obtained	Absolute error	Increase
0.1	5.89	(2, 1.68, 0.2, 19)	6.42	7.27	0.85	23.43%
0.16	5.02	(2, 1.67, 0.22, 19)	6.14	6.17	0.03	22.91%
0.26	4.58	(2, 1.68, 0.21, 15)	5.71	4.61	0.1	0.66%
0.4	2.68	(2, 1.67, 0.21, 18)	3.19	3.17	0.02	18.28%
0.63	1.41	(3, 1.69, 0.24, 17)	1.79	1.4	0.39	-0.71%
0.98	0.06	(12, 1.63, 0.3, 9)	0.42	0.05	0.37	-16.67%

TABLE III. Results of the temperature span obtained for the inverse aspect ratios considered in the simulations, before and after the application of the PS-based algorithm.

CHEX/HHEX length. The obtained maximum no-load temperature span of the initial dataset was 5.89 K. To optimize the refrigerator, we created an algorithm that is a combination of a regressor used in machine learning applications and the particle swarm algorithm. We considered three regressors (multiple linear, multilayer perceptron and gradient boosting), with the latter being selected because it generally has the largest explained variance score. The algorithm was applied to the dataset, and a global best of 6.41 K was predicted for a configuration with the smallest inverse aspect ratio ($\delta/\omega = 0.1$). The refrigerator was simulated with the predicted parameters, and a temperature span of 7.27 K was obtained, which has an absolute error of 0.85 K and represents an increase of 23.43% compared to the maximum temperature span of the 92 simulations dataset.

Although the plates had different inverse aspect ratios, we always considered the same volume of 200 mm^3 . In the following stage, the inverse aspect ratio parameter

was fixed in the algorithm, and we found the global best for the remaining inverse aspect ratios. It was possible to observe significant increases in the maximum temperature span for $\delta/\omega = 0.16$ and 0.4 , while the algorithm found values very close to the previous maximum for $\delta/\omega = 0.26$ and 0.63 . The temperature span decreases with the inverse aspect ratio and, for systems with a very large inverse aspect ratio ($\delta/\omega \approx 1$), refrigeration is almost non-existent (< 0.1 K). Even though the difference between the adiabatic temperature change obtained through the rotating and the conventional magnetocaloric effect is substantial, the values obtained reveal the potential for the development of a new class of magnetic refrigerators.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Rotating Magnetocaloric Effect

Considering the application of a magnetic flux density of $B_{appl} = 1$ T, we obtained different ΔT_{ad} , as shown in Fig. 7(a). As can be observed in Fig. 7(b), the maximum ΔT_{ad} decreases with the increase of δ/ω . Finally, we also evaluated the ratio between the maximum ΔT_{ad} obtained for each δ/ω and the maximum ΔT_{ad} obtained considering the conventional MCE when the magnetic field is applied and removed ($\Delta T_{ad}^{conv} \approx 4.22$), i.e. $\Delta T_{ad}/\Delta T_{ad}^{conv}$. The maximum ΔT_{ad} values are remarkably lower than ΔT_{ad}^{conv} and we also observe a reduction of $\Delta T_{ad}/\Delta T_{ad}^{conv}$ with the increase of δ/ω .

Algorithm Validation with Test Functions

Several mathematical benchmark test functions in the literature are used to evaluate the performance of meta-heuristic optimization algorithms. Developed to solve minimization problems, these functions were designed with multiple local minima and one global minimum to verify if, during the iterative process, the current solution(s) manage to escape the local minima and after how many iterations the global minimum is found [61, 72, 73]. Since we are dealing with a maximization problem (maximizing the refrigerator temperature span), we considered the negative of the test functions to try to find the global maximum and escape the local maxima. Although to optimize the performance of the refrigerator, we are dealing with a 5D problem (5 inputs), as a first approach and to simplify, we considered 2D test functions (2 inputs). Thus, the number of dimension is defined as $d = 2$.

Regression algorithms were not applied to this test because our goal was to evaluate if the parameters chosen for the particle swarm algorithm ensure the convergence of the particles. Thus, we considered four different functions as the objective function to validate our particle swarm-based algorithm. First, we considered the Sphere function, which has a global minimum at $(x, y) = (0, 0)$ with value 0 [72, 73]:

FIG. 7. (a) Adiabatic temperature change for different δ/ω . (b) Maximum adiabatic temperature change and $\Delta T_{ad}/\Delta T_{ad}^{conv}$ as a function of δ/ω .

$$g(x, y) = x^2 + y^2, \quad (27)$$

with $x, y \in [-5.12, 5.12]$. We also considered the Rastrigin function, which has several local minima with regular distributed locations. Similarly to the previous function, this one has a global minimum at $(x, y) = (0, 0)$ with value 0, and is described by [72, 73]:

$$g(x, y) = 10d + x^2 - 10 \cdot \cos(2\pi x) + y^2 - 10 \cdot \cos(2\pi y), \quad (28)$$

with $x, y \in [-5.12, 5.12]$. The Styblinski-Tang function, which has three local minima and a global minimum approximately at $(x, y) = (-2.903534, -2.903534)$, with value $-39.16599d$. The Styblinski-Tang function in 2D form is written as [72, 73]:

$$g(x, y) = \frac{1}{2} [x^4 - 16x^2 + 5x + y^4 - 16y^2 + 5y], \quad (29)$$

with $x, y \in [-5, 5]$. Finally, we considered the Schwefel function, which is characterized by its complex landscape

FIG. 8. 3D representation of the resulting surface for the negative of Sphere, Rastrigin, Styblinski-Tang and Schwefel functions, used to test the optimization algorithm.

and has several local minima. The global minimum is located at $(420.9687, 420.9687)$ and the function is defined by [72, 73]:

$$g(x, y) = 418.9829d - \left[x \cdot \sin(\sqrt{|x|}) + y \cdot \sin(\sqrt{|y|}) \right], \quad (30)$$

with $x, y \in [-500, 500]$. Since we are dealing with maximization problems, we will evaluate $f(x, y) = -g(x, y)$ as the objective function and the global maximum of each function will have the same location as the previous cases. Figure 8 shows the 2D version of each negative of the test function, each one with a global maximum (global best) to locate to test the proposed algorithm.

We randomly generated a sample of 500 particles with random position $\mathbf{X} = (x, y)$ and velocity \mathbf{V} . The position was determined by taking into account the search space in which each function $f(x, y)$ is defined, and the velocity range is about 10% of the position range. We set 2000 iterations to ensure that the particles converge in the

same position.

Figure 9 shows the results of the convergence of 30 particles to the global best of each test function. The particles converged to the global best in all cases before the 2000 iterations. For the negative sphere function, the particles converged at the global best at $(x, y) = (-4.57 \cdot 10^{-114}, -9.28 \cdot 10^{-114})$ with value 0, after 9 iterations. For the negative Rastrigin function, convergence occurred at the global best of $(x, y) = (-3.21 \cdot 10^{-10}, -3.18 \cdot 10^{-11})$ with value 0, after 79 iterations. In the case of the negative Styblinski-Tang function, convergence was reached after 28 iterations at the position $(x, y) = (-2.903534, -2.903534)$, with the value $-39.16599d$. Finally, for the negative Schwefel function, it converged after 26 iterations to the position $(x, y) = (420.9687, 420.9687)$, thus obtaining the global best. Since it was possible to escape local maxima and locate the global maximum of each function using the algorithm, we demonstrated that the algorithm is efficient in solving different optimization problems.

FIG. 9. Convergence of 30 particles to the global best for the negative of (a) Sphere, (b) Rastrigin, (c) Styblinski-Tang and (d) Schwefel functions.

Predicting results with GB regressor

After obtaining the global best of the swarm with the coordinates $\mathbf{X} = (2, 1.68, 0.2, 0.1, 19)$, we performed two measurements where we varied only the parameter of the period (Fig. 10). In the particular case of $\delta/\omega = 0.1$, the temperature span decreases with the period when we fixed the remaining parameters (v , d and L_{CHEX}/HH_{EX}). The absolute error for the two cases is relatively low, being 0.49 and 0.54 K for $P = 12$ and 24 s, respectively. Similarly, we varied d while the other parameters were fixed, and obtained a larger error. For

$d = 0.4$ and 0.6 mm we have 0.88 and 1.52 K, respectively. Although the regressor successfully predicts the decrease of ΔT with the period, the regressor predicts that $\Delta T(d = 0.4) > \Delta T(d = 0.6)$, which is the opposite to what was obtained in the simulations. It is expected that $d = 0.4$ and 0.6 mm have very close temperature spans (5.21 and 5.07 K) and, in the simulation, $\Delta T = 6.1$ and 6.59 K were obtained for each one. More simulations would be necessary to improve the fitting of the GB regressor. However, the primary goal of this work was to use the GB regressor as an objective function in the context of PSO to determine the best possible solution, which was successfully achieved.

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FIG. 10. Comparison between the simulated and predicted results using the GB regressor.

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